

A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO IMPROVE THE COMPETENCE OF THE ANALYSIS OF A WORK OF ART

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Abstract. This article analyzes works of art by means of specific methods and knowledge, skills and abilities based on a systematic approach in the educational process, aimed at a competency-based approach to the study of literature in secondary school students. skills and abilities in science. There are also recommendations for specific methods of art analysis.

Keywords: literature, approach, system, student, school, genre, work, analysis, method, originality, knowledge, skill, ability, competence, improvement.

СИСТЕМНЫЙ ПОДХОД К ПОВЫШЕНИЮ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ АНАЛИЗА ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯ

Аннотация. В данной статье проводится анализ художественных произведений посредством конкретных методов и знаний, умений и навыков, основанных на системном подходе в образовательном процессе, направленном на компетентностный подход к изучению литературы у учащихся средней школы. навыки и способности в науке. Есть также рекомендации по конкретным методам анализа искусства.

Ключевые слова: литература, подход, система, ученик, школа, жанр, произведение, анализ, метод, оригинальность, знание, умение, компетентность, совершенствование.

INTRODUCTION

The methodological basis for improving the methodology for developing students' competencies in the analysis of works of art is a systematic approach to understanding the innovative processes taking place in the current system of literary education. It reveals the mechanism of interaction and interaction of systems. According to Bepalko's definition: "a systematic approach is an approach that deals with a complete description of the structure of systemic objects, the laws of their operation and development" [97; 14-b.].

With a systematic approach introduction - goals, objectives; with output - the results of the work also imply a system with feedback from the community, parents, students, the external environment. It is necessary to clearly understand the essence of the innovation process, its boundaries, its connection with the concept of "pedagogical system" in order to further reveal its impact on the qualitative renewal of the education system. The entry of the pedagogical system into the education system as a system of the highest order is generally accepted [100, O.E.Lebedev, A.I. Subetto et al.].

The subject of reading literature in secondary schools operates as one of the leading disciplines in the system of mental and moral formation of schoolchildren. In this regard, the methodology of literary education should focus on the combination of traditional and innovative approaches to learning. The system of forming in students the competence of analyzing a work of art is new. According to this concept, pre-vocational training is a necessary step in building students' own learning trajectory in grades 10-11. Motivational for students is that students achieve different results in writing essays, participating in competitions, speaking at various events, implementing projects.

An important condition for the organization of vocational training is a pedagogical system of support for students (mainly grades 10-11) by primary school teachers, teacher-psychologists, classroom teachers, who help them to choose after completing basic general education.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

So, as part of the implementation of improving the competence of analyzing a work of art in students, additional courses in grades 10-11, independent work will help to solve the problem of teaching the student to be responsible.

A high-level study of literature preserves the basic foundations of science, systematizes educational ideas about the historical development of literature, and allows students to gain a deep and comprehensive understanding of the relationship between classical and modern literature. Solves problems of formation of students' reading skills, development of oral and written speech culture through the analysis of works of art "[191, p. 6]. To deepen the study of literature by focusing on its humanitarian content, the current relevance of the topics given in the literature program: to give an understanding of the importance of humanistic knowledge, humanistic consciousness and, accordingly, humanistic thinking. Literature plays the most important role in the formation of personality; introduction of additional literature training courses that create conditions for differentiating the content of education of secondary school students and take into account their abilities, personal inclinations, needs, as well as psychological and age characteristics; in-depth study of the artistic world of the author's works, focusing on the periodic aspects of the work. Stimulates students' independent thinking through comparative analysis of works of art in literary education, forms analytical thinking; the study of literature is done through the prism of the student's cognition.

In the process of teaching literature in grades 10-11, the methodological system of improving the methodology of developing students' competencies in the analysis of works of art is a structure that includes the purpose, content, methods, forms and tools of teaching and lesson design (development).

A model of a methodological system for implementing the theoretical results obtained during the study was developed. The organizational-structural model developed to improve the methodology of developing students' analysis of works of art in literature classes consists of "motivational", "knowledge", "activity" and "strategic" components and includes elements such as goals, approaches, principles, stages. The model also reflects the results achieved and the criteria for determining the development of the competence of the analysis of the work of art, as well as an ordered scheme that determines the level (Figure 2.1).

In scientific research, the model mainly serves to reveal the pedagogical process and outcome. The effective organization of the process of developing students' competence in the analysis of a work of art is interrelated with the chosen approaches, conditions.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Today, education focused on traditional lessons is much less effective. Therefore, education should focus on the formation of core competencies in graduates. Also, the introduction of competency-based education allows students to solve their own problems.

Students' ability to independently analyze a work of art and acquire new knowledge, identify problems, work with different sources, advance ideas and hypotheses as a result of searching for the most rational solutions to problems and projects, skills of art analysis are formed gradually, systematically.

Competences in the analysis of a work of art are a set of characteristics that combine knowledge, abilities, skills, movement, learning and knowledge in the field of artistic analysis. The process of shaping students' artistic analysis competencies should be a well-thought-out, purposeful system that combines different forms of routine and extracurricular activities.

The ability to independently and actively seek solutions to new problems is formed in a variety of activities. The school may create conditions for the development of such skills in the academic literature, but in a different form than in the traditional subject, especially in the development of competencies [182, 36]. classroom study of works of art, independent reading is effective in literary education. The development of a didactic tool that integrates the educational project determines the quality of teaching and learning, which in turn allows the development and improvement of literary analysis skills. Goal setting and activity planning;

- search for the necessary information, acquire the necessary knowledge;
- research (hypothesis, analysis, synthesis, detail and generalization);

Taking into account the above, we determine the competence of students in the analysis of the work of art in the study of twentieth-century Uzbek novels.

In improving their competencies, students should be able to identify and formulate key concepts in the works (object, topic, goal, task, relevance, hypothesis, methods, practical value, etc.), have a clear idea of artistic analysis, analyze, compare, generalize and draw conclusions, be able to present the results of the analysis.

The analysis of modern literary applications is carried out in order to determine the methodological sequence. At the final stage of school literary education (11th grade) the creative heritage of the writers and poets of "Uzbek literature of the XX century" is studied. The study of the works of the representatives of the "Literature of the Independence Period" in the 11th grade literature program in different ways, as well as the presence of national literary heritage in the works of writers of this period allows students to form competencies. In the 11th grade program, the study of Abdulhamid Cholpon's work "Night and Day" using specific methods, that is, the analysis of the "character of the images" shows effective results. In short, along with improving the competence of analyzing a work of art, students also develop the skills of writing reviews of read novels. Generality and genres of the 10th grade literature textbook, a rough plan for the analysis of the genre specificity of a literary work; identifying characters in different genres of literary work is an "analysis of the genre specificity of a literary work". In our opinion, it is necessary to create a model that suggests the content and methodology of studying the artistic heritage of writers "Independence period literature", taking into account the short story texts that significantly improve the knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies of schoolchildren, help to get acquainted with the legacy of writers of the twentieth century.

In developing a system of classrooms for the study of the next Uzbek novels of the twentieth century, the teacher must take into account the need to adequately provide students with a methodologically sound reading process (from cognition to thinking). In such circumstances, teachers are able to allow a competent student to read the work freely and with interest, to make a detailed, reasoned judgment about what they have read.

It should be noted that this method is built taking into account the age and intellectual characteristics of school students. It is important to develop the interest of school students in the work of art. For example, the interpretation of works studied by students in grades 8-9 and 10-11 is a period of improving previously acquired interpretive knowledge and skills.

Twentieth-century Uzbek literature shows that the works of art selected for study should reflect the important cultural and historical significance of the appeal of local writers to the novel in the next period of the twentieth century.

Thus, the rise of the novel genre in the Uzbek literature of the twentieth century, in our opinion, is associated with a period of profound spiritual changes in the public consciousness, the acquisition of ideas and the search for answers to the most pressing political, moral, legal, philosophical and religious questions. Therefore, at the school stage it is necessary to acquaint high school students with the peculiarities and types of works of the twentieth century (prose and poetic forms). Abdulla Qodiri's novel "Last Days", ie his contribution to the "History of Uzbek culture", as well as the system of lessons and extracurricular activities gradually form in the reader's ideas about the novelist Abdullah Qodiri, his contribution to the Uzbek literary process. It provides the necessary basis for the perception that they are still unknown and allows them to be understood in the later stages of the study of the genre. Such an approach allows us to see the differences between the positions of both local and twentieth-century local writers, as well as the positions reflected in the studied novels of different authors. zusi. In the problem approach, how does Abdullah Qadiri solve the "eternal" problem of respect for human dignity? To define the scope of these problems, it is necessary to rely on traditional themes in the methodology of teaching literature and school practice: love, homeland, loneliness, destiny and destiny, women's lives, friendship, freedom and others.

DISCUSSION

In the 10th grade, it is advisable to organize an introductory lesson before studying the novel "Last Days" for these purposes. In this introductory lesson, the tasks set in the curriculum are partially solved: Abdulla Qodiri is the founder of Uzbek novels; Abdullah Qadiri's contribution to the establishment of the realistic method in Uzbek prose; The role of the novel "Last Days" in the spiritual life of the nation in the twentieth century; issues such as the novel's creative history and destiny will be covered in a 30-minute introductory session. During the lesson, the teacher of literary criticism O.Sharafutdinov, U.Normatov, N. If you read some excerpts from Karimov's pamphlets and articles on "Last Days," the lesson will be even more meaningful.

It is also useful to cite interesting information from the historical documentary "About my father" by Habibullo Qadiri, son of Abdullah Qadiri, and "Buried without a head" by the poet Shukrullo. Literary albums, works, press materials, works of literary scholars dedicated to the life and work of the writer are selected as teaching aids, which are well exhibited in the classroom and presented to students. The melody and song composed of Mashrab's ghazali "Ortar" from the magnetic tape are played softly. The teacher reads an episode from the novel about Otabek's arrival in the bar, calling the musician and asking him to play a tune, and having a painful experience. What events caused Otabek to fall into such a situation? What kind of person is Otabek? What about the half he cared about? What is the history of the events that took place? Where is the "knot" of the problem? Students with problem-solving questions begin to answer the questions. Inadequate answers are filled by other students, and all feedback is led by the teacher. At the next stage of the lesson, students will be given samples of portraits and place drawings from the text of the work.

"In the net of the palace, one of the more beautiful rooms is covered with felt, and in the other room there are red carpets, and in others there are gray and adras blankets. In the other room there are candles. the owner of this cell is also created differently "

"He's a young man with a heavy nature, a big body, a handsome and white face, handsome black eyes, well-proportioned black eyebrows and a fresh mustache. So this cell was remarkable in terms of both building and equipment oil, as well as in terms of ownership. Otabek is the son of Yusufbek Haji, one of the famous officials of Tashkent.

"One of these two men was a small, full-faced man with a small beard, a young man of about twenty-five years of age. was an unsightly man who was young. Although this young man is a good statesman, but for some reason his fame is not with his wealth, he is known as "Homid wife". "Mirzakarim was about forty-five or fifty years old. He had black eyebrows, black eyes, a beautiful face, and was well-dressed. Akrom Haji was an old man of fifty-five."

"There are two women on each side of the tancha: one of them is wearing a satin shirt, the other is wearing an odmi khan satin guppi, he is wearing a white dakan on his head, he is thirty-five years old, a beautiful woman. The wife of the savior is Mother Sunshine, the other is an old woman in her seventies, the mother of Mother Sunshine is Aunt Aisha. At the top of the stove, another woman, about forty-five years old, is making tea. "This woman is the maid of the family - Toybeka."

"... we see a girl lying awake in the arms of a satin bed, a pair of pillows in a net, melted by the cold or for some other reason. Her black eyebrows fluttered erratically on either side of the pillow, her dark eyes under her dark lashes stared at one point, as if she had seen something, a black bow, her graceful, crooked eyebrows twitched, as if frightened of something. his white face, as dusty as a full moon, turned a little red, as if embarrassed by someone Her average chest was slightly raised above the yellow ruffled satin dress. When he got up, he shook his head and nodded. Behind the tremor, he wrapped his face in hairless strands and took a lifeless photo. The angel in the picture was the Silver Maiden's daughter. "[53]

What can you say about the style and skill of the writer Abdullah Qadiri through the portrait taken from the text of the work in your hands? Why did Qadiri try to create portraits of different heroes from the first page of the novel? After listening to the students 'feedback, the next question may arise: Can you imagine what artistic colors Qadiri used to create the portrait? For what purpose did the writer use artistic colors?

The discussion continues with the following questions: handouts are now distributed to other students, with examples of dialogues between the protagonists of the novel. Through dialogues between the protagonists, students should be able to interpret the human image of each, based on their inner world. Discussion - Other students can also participate in the discussion, complementing the comments made, or come up with new views on the question based on their own evidence.

"I don't think there's anything more delicate in the world than getting married," said Rahmat and turned to Otabek. When he gets married, it is very good if it suits his wife's taste; otherwise there will be no such thing in the world. "Our will to marry," said Rahmat, "is to be pleasing to the sons of the brides whom our parents have taken from us." It is not the custom of the bridegroom and the bridesmaids to say that this is a good and lawful thing to do. For example, I said: I got married to my parents' likes ... but even if my wife is suitable for my parents, it is not suitable for me. "Otabek sincerely welcomes Rahmat's words. "There is no

doubt that you are right," he said. "There is no need to be suitable for a wife or not," Homid protested. "The name 'husband' is enough for women. But as my nephew said, if it suits the place called wife." "Nephew," said Homid, looking at Rahmat, "there is no point in marrying for the sake of your parents and resenting them." As long as it does not suit your wife, take her accordingly and make her double. If they don't agree, take the third one. " These dialogues shed light on which aspect of the worldview of all three individuals. It turned out that the protagonists of the work expressed their views on the issue of marriage. So who do you support and why? Did Otabek do the right thing by bowing for parental consent? What would you have done instead?

After the questions have been covered, the teacher summarizes the ideas and draws the students' attention to the plates from which the image of nature is given from the novel: for what purpose do you think the writer used the image of nature in the play? "The insatiable blue carpets of the bottomless hills and the healing smells that are forced on their nostrils can make any life-giving person feel at ease, even if only a little. These flowers will also attract Otabek, who is floating in his lap. " "Now the days of spring: hills, mountains, streams ... again, with so many colorful flowers, they give new life and new hope to their lovers, who are barely able to cope with the cold winter."

When Otabek obeys his parents' wishes, he is left in the throes of separation, emigration and suffering. At this time, the writer skillfully used their letters to vividly express the experiences of Otabek and Kumush.

What aspects of the character of Otabek and Silver did you learn through the letters written by the two beloved souls?

After the students have expressed their independent opinions, their attention is drawn to the writer's skill in creating national characters in the novel.

In literature, the issue of nationality has always been in the focus of literary critics and studied. It is no coincidence that "Last Days" was recognized as the first Uzbek national novel. Skillful use of the Uzbek literary language to reflect national characters, national spirit; it is a great creative achievement of the writer to be able to depict the scenes of national life, customs, morals from the point of view of national culture. It is clear from the very beginning that the main goal of the author is to bring the Uzbek folklore, the national spirit of classical literature to the novel genre. In his work, the writer embodied the national way of life, the problems of everyday life, reflecting the national spirit and national thinking, and managed to revive the image of Otabek, Kumush, Mirzakarim kutidor, Yusufbek Haji at the level of national characters. These aspects of the writer's work are first of all covered by Oybek, and since the 60s in the researches, pamphlets and monographs of such literary scholars as A.Aliev, M.Kushjanov, S.Mirvaliev, I.Mirzaev, H.Lutfiddinova, U.Normatov.

Thus, in the novel, the image of the historical period is intertwined with the image of living conditions, creating a historical-national calorie in the work. These signs of historical and living conditions have become an important factor in shaping the way of thinking, the national image of the heroes. In a work of art, the poetic image as the core of the artist's artistic and aesthetic potential reflects the writer's individuality and the ability to interpret spiritually and emotionally. No matter how strong the inner experience and psyche in the poetic image, which combines the writer's worldview, reality and the way of artistic discovery of man, it is connected with real life and people's aspirations. Thinking through an artistic image is creative in nature, in

which the spirit of a particular historical period, the mood of the people, and the features of aesthetic thinking are also significantly influenced.

Therefore, it is natural that in the essence of the poetic image there are changes related to the stages of social development and the needs of the spiritual-literary environment. A poetic image can be a specific manifestation of the human psyche, but it can also consist of an object, an object, a natural phenomenon. Importantly, he can rise to the level of a poetic image only if he illuminates the psyche of the protagonist in all its complexity in the work of art, embodies the ideological and artistic intentions of the writer and becomes the fulcrum of the pathos of the work.

The thematic content of the problem is much broader in the works of art in the program of the twentieth century. The works of art offered for study are not complete, but can be modified and supplemented at the request of the teacher and students. At the same time, these topics, in our opinion, correspond to the level of psychological and intellectual development, as well as the interests of high school students. The principle of continuity is related to previous topics, as it involves the study of a particular writer's work (or the poetics of a work of art genre) in close connection with an existing tradition. The principle of continuity helps to develop and deepen students' holistic understanding of the literature of the period being studied. It allows students to rely on existing knowledge and ideas about the specifics of the genre to further develop their art analysis competencies. This is especially important for the gradual formation of knowledge about the poetics of the novel genre and its peculiarities in different historical-literary periods.

The principle of variability is that the list of studied literary texts may be overstated and that the teacher's system of classroom and extracurricular activities (including elective courses) may change the construction sequence in the teaching practice. This need may arise in "emergencies" in the classroom, when a heated discussion on a particular issue forces the teacher to return to the problem being discussed in the new material, redistributing the hours scheduled to study a particular topic to show him or her other approaches. There is also a need to stratify the list of works of art, which in turn helps to take into account the student's interests, level of knowledge and abilities. The principle of "synthesis of works of art" and artistic preferences of schoolchildren. Such an approach is consistent with the age characteristics of the perception of a work of art by high school students. Using the means of expression of different types of art, the reader can independently interpret the idea of a work of art through the prism of his own perception.

CONCLUSION

In our research, the work of Erkin Vahidov and Rauf Parfi stands out. The uniqueness of Erkin Vahidov's poems "Rebellion of souls", Rauf Parfi's poem "Dawn", "Rain", "Summer night", "I'm back", "Heart" requires study because the lyrics of a writer's prose can be interpreted in a unique way by the reader depending on the perception and analysis of the work. Differentiated education is a didactic principle, according to which a set of conditions is created to increase efficiency, taking into account the typological characteristics of students (interests, creativity, learning, learning ability, performance, etc.), according to which educational goals, content, forms and methods of teaching are selected. and stratified; the essence of the activity of developing students' competence in the analysis of a work of art is that school literary research is based on the joint research and creative work of the student and the teacher, the solution of the

problem of the work of art, the goal is a new intellectual product. The study of information in school curricula should be based on a specific approach, ie the gradual transition of the main stages, and should be aimed at improving students' competence in the analysis of the work of art; the unity of extracurricular and extracurricular activities implies their close relationship, interpretation, development of creative, independent, enterprising activities of students, various forms of work that provide the formation of the mental and emotional world of the student.

At the same time, the unity of extracurricular and extracurricular activities implies their close interrelationships, their interpretation, the various principles of work that run through the general principles and methodological aspects of the selection of works of art. In our methodology, extracurricular and extracurricular activities are not separate classes from each other, but complex structures that are elements of a system of literary education of school students.

All of the above is the psychological, pedagogical, methodological and literary basis for the creation of a methodology for the study of the next national novel of the twentieth century in school literary education, aimed at improving students' competence in analyzing a work of art.

Based on the improvement of students' competence in the analysis of a work of art, in literary education students are given a personal-oriented approach to the development of their new intellectual product. Students gain experience in creating new intellectual products, the results of which are reflected in the implementation of new projects and presentations, participation in school readers' competitions and other forms of work in the novel genre.

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